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lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

JENNY L. LABINDAO, MAEd

Teacher III

Patimbao Elementary School

Deped Santa Cruz, Laguna

Region IV – A, CALABARZON, Philippines

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**Teaching, Touching Lives, Finding Purpose:
My 18-year journey as an Educator**

It began in 2008. I had just given birth to my one and only princess, my daughter. She was only a month old, but I had to be present in school for the first day of classes. I was just employed as a permanent public-school teacher month prior. In my mind, I felt that I had no right to a maternity leave. I stormed through rainy days to attend to the needs of my Kindergarten pupils. It rained almost every day in the first months, giving me a sign that it will not be a walk in the clouds, being a primary teacher for I have finished a course that is not aligned with what I'm doing. I should be a secondary Math teacher, and yet I am dealing with younger kids every day; Wide-eyed, all ears, uncontrollable tantrums scattered and minds that are just beginning to grasp the realities of life as pupils. Some of them do not even know how to count, too amazed to see how the letters of the alphabet look like.

I was met with different challenges. Some parents were supportive, but others weren't exactly interested in dealing with matters such as their kids' academic standing. It was a shock right away, not knowing where to start. The development and strategies I learned during seminars and through articles read seemed to be too rigid and were not applicable. I felt like giving up due to various reasons, pressure, fatigue, and the realization of being an outcast in the field I once dreamed of.

I had to study again, not in a university or college but in the same classroom where I teach. I used my interest in psychology to deal with the difficulty of the pupils, some of them in dire need of attention and love. In the first school year of being a Kinder teacher, I learned that it is not easy, but I can do something. No matter how small it is, to help mold young minds. I saw how they developed, not only in their growth but also their progress in every aspect. It's like magic, but not in the blink of an eye. It takes time. It requires action not from a magician but from an educator with a motherly love.

Printed teaching materials should be colorful and unusually big. My way of communicating with them should be a little bit animated. The energy from the morning session should not falter until the end of the afternoon session. Time should always be a reminder to all of them of the need to go to school the following day so as not to miss interesting lessons and fun activities, games and prizes in which all came from my pocket, which is, although not that full, is more than willing to share a candy or two to all of them.

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My profession became a mission. I felt proud seeing each class graduate. They all deserve a beaming round of applause. Deep in my heart, a burst of emotion always surged; a combination of happiness, pride, and loneliness. Another batch will leave me. Will they still remember me next year? Will they go back to my classroom to hold my hand, and bid their farewell before going home? Will they carry the torch of eagerness to learn after building foundations on reading, writing and character values under my care?

From teaching Kindergarten, I was offered to transfer to a higher-grade level. Grade 1 was not that different from my first assignment, but it presented itself as a greater challenge. I integrated the mentality of “Babasa para makapasa”, and “Sama-samang matuto para sa pagbabago.” The mission of teaching young learners as of now is not only a profession, but a huge part of my identity as a person. Guiding these kids although not my own, feels honorable, as I can serve them in my own way. No matter what the consequences are. Being in the same school for these eighteen years, working with almost the same faces as my co-teachers would call it is a blessing. Giving back to my alma mater, Patimbao Elementary School fills my heart with great joy.

Looking back at the years I spent, I have no regrets. Its lasting impact on how I live my life will continue, and I remain in this field, willing to help develop young minds in the years to come. The continuation of my journey is something I truly look forward to, and I am truly excited of what the future holds for me in this institution.